

A Research into the Factors That Influence Job Satisfaction Among Millennial Health Workers in Ghana: A Case of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital Ghana

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There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Previous organizations focused only on profit margins, turnover, diversification and globalization. Recently, however, strategic planning companies have realized that their obligation is to improve employee job satisfaction. In recent years, social organizations and institutions have significantly increased their attention to employee satisfaction, especially for millennials. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to explore the influencing factors of job satisfaction in millennials. This paper puts forward four dependent variables: work-life balance, working conditions, leadership style, organizational culture; five demographic variables: gender, age, income level, employment level, education level; 1 independent variable: job satisfaction. The data collected in this paper are mainly through the questionnaire survey and analysis, regression analysis and the use of econometric models. The paper designs and methods the data deployment used to obtain a sample of 200 millennials working at KATH. In this study, the structured model was used to analyze the impact of employee participation on job satisfaction, and how different forms of participatory decision-making in the workplace led to individual satisfaction with the objective and internal aspects of work. Frequency, descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, reliability and validity were extracted by SPSS software. The Cronbach alpha values of each subscale were 0.9412 ~ 0.958, indicating that the scale had high internal consistency and reliability. The results of the study highlight that there is a positive correlation between employee input and job satisfaction for millennials. There is a higher correlation between employee job satisfaction and millennials' participation in general decisions in each company. participation and job satisfaction in the context of developing countries. This study is of great significance in various disciplines and in certain areas, such as research practice and policy. This study is helpful to the mutual benefit of human resources management, especially in the management of hospital workers or other similar organizations.

Keyword: JOB SATISFACTION, MILLENNIAL, HEALTH WORKER BEHAVIOR, GHANA

Introduction

The entire world's economy has established how the millennial generation has very small commitment to organization because of factors that connects to the intrinsic and extrinsic issues related to occupation contentment. There is a vital concern for job satisfaction among millennial today, HRM leaders are all the time looking ways to guarantee that their staff are satisfied. By using the technique of measuring, the report examined the connection between the inherent and the extrinsic reasons together with the significant facets of the organizational dedication. More often the economy and its economic fluctuations has influenced businesses and scholars of the world to consider its most important resource, individuals (Azeez, S.A.2017). That, if health worker's satisfaction are being reached, a delightful motion of fullness is accomplished. So therefore, the concept of job satisfaction through workers faceless surveys became cliché in the 1930s (Letham, G.P and Budworth, M.H, 2007). Again, there has been no doubt that in order to sustain competitive advantage between the global economies, leaders need to look beyond capital resources. But rather, health organizations or top management should evaluate the culture of their human capital to sustain competitive advantage (Ting 1997). Due to the global pandemic shift, the composition of health labor force is also changing rapidly which tend to affect millennial's as well. And majority of the health work forces in the health industry nowadays are possessed by millennial's, who were born between year 1984 and 1996 (Gursoy *et al.*, 2013). The traditionalists (people conceived 1945 and before) view, Baby Boomers (people conceived near 1946 and 1964), X generation (people, primarily conceived 14 near 1965 and 1978), and Millennial/Y Generation (people conceived between 1984 and 2000). Millennial's are known to be self-focused and transitory but also educated, fierce and careerfocused therefore, understanding of their characteristics and knowing how to satisfy them present a substantial topic for both researchers and health practitioners. In as much, recent times has shown, how both the organizations and societies have significantly increased their focus on job satisfaction for their employees. (Tomažević, N.; Seljak, J.; Aristovnik, A.2014). Human Resource Management (HRM) should improve their human resource activities such as off site training practices and welfare services in hospitals or other forms of health care institutions in order to realize their targets regarding their staff's satisfaction. However, recent developments in job satisfaction, employers need to add more incentives that expand out from the company into society to attract Millennials (Sanghi, 2016).

Statement of problem

Any institution or business that is comprehensive of a connection with a profitable worker base and solid resolve is a formula for a superior association (Fred, N. 2017). While considering the significance of occupation fulfillment and maintenance, there is a substantial business case for critical investigation and research into what keeps workers fulfilled. The accelerated rate at which the number of retirements anticipated from the millennial age is beginning to constrain associations to look at progression arranging activities and hierarchical limit. Millennial have risen inside the personnel positions, thus considering and

distinguishing subjects that prompt occupation fulfillment and inspiration among this gathering can give critical markers that will prompt drawing in and holding this populace of experts and future pioneers. In a current occupation fulfillment overview of optional instructors, scientist Azerbaijan Baku stresses: “It is an irrefutable actuality that educators assume a crucial part in the training life of understudies”. Educators are preeminent among the individuals who affect future ages of a country. Leaders should be happy with their position keeping in mind that the end goal to satisfy their duties. (Gabriel, S. E., & Normand, S. L. T., 2012) Baku's examination and other outside components additionally light up the significance of this issue on the advanced education plan. In a given organization, a significant inquiry happens to a worker think of leaving their jobs. It is the work of the group to attempt keeping the workers they value and to treasure them as assets. The matter of employee turnover has developed a quandary worldwide. The changing culture of work and environment has become the most significant cause of individuals altering their job and many other employment circumstances. Coming to current civilization, the cohort of child boomers retire, and currently the generation-together with the Millennial enter colossal job force of the present day that everyone needs to stay movable. The generation who serves this population in health care will consist of majority of millennial. Research proves that the millennial generation have specific preferences, expectations, and values when it comes their work life. In order to reduce health workers turnover, administrators or supervisors must understand these preferences, expectations, and values to be able to give the necessary training, management, and recruitment of this generation of employees. The health sector in Ghana usually portrays public strikes, for better working conditions. These strikes cause reduction in production and services causing major problems across all sectors of the economy. According to (Bochering and Oglesby 1974), if workers expectations are met, working conditions are improved hence increase in satisfaction. Also, (Cotton et al., 2005) concluded that if work satisfaction is improved, is the key to sustainable development across all public sectors of the country. Therefore, there is an importance to investigate the factors that influences job satisfaction among millennial in the public health sector and refer to them to improve job satisfaction among them. This paper, therefore, sets out to seek and achieve this in the Ghanaian health sector.

Objective of the study

In order to improve health services in Ghana, the main purpose of the study is to ascertain the factors affecting job satisfaction among Millennial in the Public Health sector Ghana. There are also other minor objectives that the study seeks to find. For this purpose, the following work is investigated;

1. To investigate millennial attitude towards their salary, promotion and job satisfaction.
2. To find out how the relationship between Millennial and the older generation (demographic variables) determine their job satisfaction.
3. To analyze the extent to which leadership styles influences Millennial job satisfaction.
4. To establish whether Working Conditions determines health workers job satisfaction in Ghana, which may be relative in stimulating economic growth.

Research questions

This current study seeks to find answers to these questions.

1. How does working conditions influence employee job satisfaction Millennial in the Health sector of Ghana.
2. What are Millennial attitudes towards their salary, promotion and job satisfaction?
3. How does the relationship between Millennial and their older coworkers (demographic variables) influence their job satisfaction?
4. What is the extent to which leadership styles (supervisors and team leaders) determine job satisfaction?

Statement of hypothesis

1. Work-life balance has direct significant positive influence on employee job satisfaction.
2. Working conditions have significant positive impact on employee job satisfaction.
3. Leadership preference has a significant positive relationship towards millennial job satisfaction in the Ghanaian Health community.
4. Organizational culture related to employees has positive impact on job satisfaction.

Significant of study

This dissertation is very significant in diverse way since many health workers especially nurses, have the tendency to quit or go on strike on their job due to the overwhelming responsibility of their work. Industry experts project that the Millennial generation will dominate majority of the global workforce by 90% by the year 2030. In industries such as media and information technology (IT), millennial already make up a huge percentage of the work force. However, job satisfaction among millennial seems not to be the ad same as their older generation. Millennial tend to get the job that have retirement options, ability to have a good family home relationship, loyalty and so on. This situation influences the management of human resource. The topic is noteworthy for a variety of reasons and as well contributes to academic, social and economic areas by explaining the determinants of job satisfaction. The study will be used by researchers and organizational policy makers in the area of Health and other human resource organizations as far as Millennials in Ghana are concerned which in the end contribute to the further understanding of the mutual benefits that comes out of job satisfaction. Lastly, the results will be of great help to the health sector and its leaders in their decision of job satisfaction strategy. Therefore, this dissertation will aid in areas like Research, Practice and lastly Policy.

Research

The study will add to the buildup of knowledge in literature in this field for further research on this topic or related ones.

Practice

It will also contribute the external users understanding of the of mutual benefits that come out with ways means to enable organizations to achieved job satisfaction.

Policy

It will also be decision makers in the area of Human Resource Management (HRM) relating to health to achieve organizational job satisfaction to ensure efficiency and effectiveness of its workers.

Materials and methods

Research Design

This was a quantitative study that used a border census. The survey will be performed using a 5-likert questionnaire and will be completed utilizing online survey technique. These surveys have already been field-tested to ensure that there are no errors or omissions. The questions were both open-ended and closed-ended in character.

Study area

The study was carried out using one of the biggest public hospitals in Ghana Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital (KATH) in Kumasi, a major town in the Ashanti Region of Ghana. Kumasi is a Municipal Assembly with the population of about 1,500,000 as at 2020 population census. Kumasi is the administrative capital of the Kumasi Municipal Assembly, and it attracts attention due to the presence of high-end enterprises, private health institutions and organizations. Kumasi is home to a large number of young people who live and work there. This town was picked because of the amount of accessible health institutions , the quality of people living there, and the huge number of millennials who live there. The targeted population for the study is employees (millennials) working at KATH Ghana in Kumasi Metropolis. That is the millennial working at Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital.

Sample Size

When the constituents of a population are not identical in every way, it is said to be multifarious. That is, while all of the elements fulfill the rest of the requirements that characterize the target population, one distinctive variable differs among them. As a result, the study's target demographic was homogenized because it consisted of health workers working for the same hospital. Survey was conducted based on their long-term experience with KATH. A high sample size was also chosen since the sample must be representative of the entire population working in the hospital. Following the completion of the intended investigation, the outcomes were properly extrapolated to the study. The sample size for the study comprised two hundred (200) employees or workers of KATH within the Kumasi Adum district.

Sampling method and sources of data

The study was able to determine the specific healthcare personnel of KATH inside the millennial age gap using the basic random sample, convenient, and purposive sampling techniques used in this study. Primary data sources were used in this analysis. The volunteers, who are KATH's millennial employees, were the major source of data, which was gathered through the use of questionnaires.

Sources of data

The researcher used two sorts of data to meet the study's goal and answer the research questions: primary and secondary data. The primary source of data was obtained from the participants that is the millennial employees of KATH through the administering of questionnaires. Secondary data were obtained from Ghana health statistical journals, articles, books and statistical reports from the hospital database and other online health publications on employee work satisfaction , health workers turnover in the field of human resource labor.

Research instrument and analysis

Questionnaires were used as a preliminary data gathering tool in this investigation. With the help of SPSS 18, the filled surveys were decalogued. Other statistical tools, such as Microsoft Excel, was utilized to analyze the data. Frequencies, descriptive statistics, regression correlation, and summary statistics were used in this study. The replies to the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The researcher was able to better comprehend levels of satisfaction by converting the replies to each of the questionnaire's questions into the number of times a certain answer occurred. The reliability of our data gathering tools would be assessed using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient (r). Also, the demographic data from the questionnaire was presented in the form of tables.

Results

Survey questions that were distributed and collected, with all of them being suitable for analysis, were two hundred (200) in total. All respondents were health workers of Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital (KATH) within the millennial age gap and more importantly been working at KATH for a minimum of 2 years. The research study focused on influences of job satisfaction amongst millennial. The demographic profile used frequencies to determine the number of times a particular question was answered.

Respondent's gender

The only goal of the gender segment of the population was to display the ratio of males and females who completed the questionnaires in percentile rank.

Table 1 Gender Response

Gender	Distribution	Percentile rank
Female	80	40.0
Male	120	60.0
TOTAL	200	100

Table 1 reveals that of the 200 total health workers, 120 were men, indicating a response rate of 60 percent, and 40 percent were females, totaling 80 people. The sample included both gender participants, though the preponderance were men.

Health workers age

Table 2 Age response

Age	Distribution	Percentile rank
18-25	60	30.00
26-35	80	40.00
36-45	40	20.00
46 -50	20	10.00
TOTAL	200	100

As seen in the table above, age was separated into four segments. The majority of health workers were between the ages of 26 and 35, accounting for 40% of the target population; followed by those between the ages of 18 and 25, accounting for 30%, those between the ages of 36 and 45, and those between the ages of 46 and 50, accounting for 20% and 10% of the sample population, correspondingly, 40 and 20 health workers.

Health workers educational level

Table 3 Educational level response

Educational	Distribution	Percentile rank
Bachelors	80	40
Postgraduate	60	30
Doctorate	60	30
Total	200	100

Within the sample size, the table above shows the educational levels of health workers. The chart reveals that a sizable percentage of health workers have a slightly elevated degree of education and hence are capable of making well-informed diagnoses about their patients' healthcare. The percentage of the participants had completed at least a bachelor's degree, accounting for 40% of the entire targeted population.

Health workers employment level

Table 4 Employment level (Job Designation)

Job Designation	Distribution	Percentile rank
Midwives	60	30
Nurses	120	60
Doctors	20	10
Total	200	100

As seen in the table above, employment was classified into three groups. 60 respondents were classified as midwives, accounting for 30% of the sample population; 120 respondents were classified as nurses, accounting for 60% of the sample population. Doctors were represented by 10% of the participants, totalling 20 health workers.

Health workers income level

Table 5 Respondents' Monthly Income level

Income	Distribution	Percentile rank
Less than \$600	80	40
\$600- \$1000	80	40
\$1000-above	40	20
Total	200	100

Table 5 reveals that of the total of 200 health workers, 80 obtained less than \$600 per month, generating a response rate of 40%, while another 40% obtained between \$600 and \$1000 per month, providing a classification accuracy of 40%. A total of 40 people, or 20% of the respondents, got more than \$1000 every month.

To characterize the link between each independent variable and the dependent variable, a separate regression of each independent variable was computed (Lamelas, 2011). As a result, the multiple regression model employed in this research is as follows:

$$JS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * WLB + \beta_2 * WC + \beta_3 * LS + \beta_4 * OrgCul + \beta_5 * Inc + \beta_5 * + \beta_6 * EDL + \epsilon \text{ Where:}$$

β_0 - Is constant term

β_1 – is the Coefficient of Work-Life Balance

β_2 – is the Coefficient of Working Conditions

β_3 – is the Coefficient of Leadership Styles

β_4 – is the Coefficient of Organizational Culture

β_5 – is the Coefficient of Employees's Income

β_6 – is the Coefficient of Employee's Level of Education Dependent variable

JS- is Job Satisfaction Independent variable

WBL- Work-Life Balance

WC- Working Conditions

LS- Leadership Styles

OrgCul- Organizational Culture Control Variables

Inc- Income

EDL- Educational Level ϵt = error term

Reliability and validity

A pretest of the questionnaire was required to ensure reliability, relevance, and content validity among respondents who were not part of the study's respondents but had extensive understanding of the study's topic. Reliability of the variables adopted in the study was tested using the Cronbach 's alpha.

Cronbach alpha coefficients

Table 6 1 Cronbach Alpha

VARIABLES	CRONBACH'S ALPHA	NO. OF ITEMS
Work-life Balance	.945	4
Working Condition	.943	4
Leadership	.944	4
Organizational Culture	.944	4
Job Satisfaction	.943	9

The internal consistency for the constituent parts of the independent and dependent variables is shown in the table above. The aforementioned results show that they fall just within the alpha coefficient range, making them suitable for distribution and analysis. All coefficients are more than 0.6, which is the minimum necessary to carry the reliability test validity.

4.3 The Correlation and Regression Analysis 4.3.1 The Correlation Analysis

Table 7 Correlation

		Income	Educational	Organizational Culture	Working conditions	Work- life balance	Leadership styles
JS	Pearson Correlation						
Income Level	Pearson Correlation	-.448**					
Educational Level	Pearson Correlation	.035NS	.129*				
Organizational Culture	Pearson Correlation	.805***	.457***	-.165***			
Working conditions	Pearson Correlation	.853***	-.413**	-.116***	.762***		
Work-life balance	Pearson Correlation	-.574**	-.436**	.325***	.698***	.440***	
Leadership styles	Pearson Correlation	.686***	-.538**	.443***	.844***	.575***	.884***
Sample (N) = 200							

***correlation is significant at $p < .001$, **correlation is significant at $p < .01$, *correlation is significant at $p < .05$

The Pearson correlation matrix values between the correlation analysis are included in the table above, indicating a causal link between the two variables. Pearson correlation figures range between 0 and 1 and are significant at the .01 and .05 level. The direction of the link between the Dependent Variable (DV) and the Independent Variable (IV) is depicted by positive and negative correlation coefficients (IVs).

Job satisfaction was shown to be significant when all of the other independent factors, such as work-life, working conditions, leadership, and organizational culture, were taken into account. Because their p-values were more than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), certain connections between the independent factors, dependent variable, and control variables were also highlighted as insignificant. This happened between Job satisfaction as a dependent variable and educational level as a control variable, which had an insignificant association of -.035 but income level had a significant association of -.448 with the dependent variable, indicating its relevance.

Hypothesis testing

Before the analysis, the four hypotheses which describes what influence the level of job satisfaction among millennial stated their significant relationship with the dependent variable. After running the analysis, the

results from the data or responses from the respondents stated that all the four hypotheses have significant relationship with the dependent variable. Below display the actual figures of the degree of the relationship.

Hypotheses H1: Examines the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction. After the test, it revealed that ($r = .57$; $p < 0.001$) thus $r = .57$ means correlation value — r depict a strong correlation. This simply signifies that there is a genuine and meaningful connection between the two. Hence, H1 is supported and also significantly correlated.

Hypotheses H2: Also investigates the link between working condition and job satisfaction. After the test, it revealed that ($r = .85$; $p < 0.001$) thus $r = .85$ means correlation value — r shows a strong correlation. This simply signifies that there is a genuine and meaningful connection between the two. Hence, H2 is supported and also significantly correlated.

Hypotheses H3: Investigates the link between leadership and job satisfaction . After the test, it revealed that ($r = .69$; $p < 0.001$) thus $r = .67$ means correlation value — r shows a positive correlation was significantly correlated This simply signifies that there is a genuine and meaningful connection between the two. Hence, H3 is supported and also significantly correlated.

Hypotheses H4: Investigates the relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction. After the test, it revealed that ($r = .81$; $p < 0.001$) thus $r = .81$ means correlation value — r shows a positive correlation was significantly correlated. This simply signifies that there is a genuine and meaningful connection between the two. Hence, H4 is supported and also significantly correlated.

In regards of the independent variables, the relationship between the variables may also be explored, as seen in the table below. The results demonstrate that organizational culture has a strong or significant link with working conditions ($r = .76$; $p < 0.001$), indicating a strong association between both. Additionally, organizational culture has a high or significant link with work-life balance in influencing job satisfaction among Ghanaian health professionals ($r = .69$; $p < 0.001$), indicating a strong association between them. When it comes to variables of work satisfaction, organizational culture has a strong or significant link with leadership ($r = .84$; $p < 0.001$), indicating a strong association between them. As a result, it may be argued that these independent factors have an impact on work satisfaction.

Ultimately, the correlation table indicates the link between the control factors and the dependent variable, as well as whether there is a connection or not, by taking into account the control variables, which are also demographic features. To begin, the chart shows that there is a negative association between health employees' pay and job happiness. As a result ($p < 0.001$) ($r = -.45$) Finally, when it comes to educational attainment, the table shows that there is no substantial relationship between educational attainment and work satisfaction. As a result, ($r = -.035$; $p < 0.001$).

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is needed, necessary, and advised to reveal the in-depth contribution and the degree to which these independent variables independently impact the dependent variable, regardless of their correlation value. A regression analysis was undertaken in order to look further into the specific contributions of each independent variable (work-life balance, working conditions, leadership, and organizational culture) to the dependent variable, job satisfaction.

The model summary is shown in the table below, which illustrates the results of the multiple regression.

Table 8 Regression

Variable	Model 1 B (unstandardized)	β (standardized)
Income level	.071	.004 NS
Educational	2.874	.197***
Work life-Balance	.016	.005 NS
Working condition	1.742	.671***
Leadership	-.092	-.039NS
Org. Culture	.950	.411***
R 2	.833	
Adjusted R2	.827	
R 2 Change	.625	
F-value	136.999	
F change	179.890	
VIF range	8.622-1.191	

Research Study in table above examined the effect of work-life balance and working conditions (i.e., independent variable) on job satisfaction in health workers in Ghana when it comes to job satisfaction that is (dependent variable). The first, the three controlling variables were defined as endogenous variable that predicted 20.8 percent of the total variability in the dependent variable while controlling for factors affecting health workers: earnings and educational attainment. In as much as correlation analysis has been conducted to show positive relationship between the independent and the dependent variables, that does not guarantee or shows the outcome of the regression analysis.

In regression, the outcome may turn to be either positive or negative depending on their degree of relationship. In this dissertation, the table's beta values also reflect the order in which independent variables have an influence on health professionals' behavior when it comes to job satisfaction. It shows that working conditions ($\beta=.67$) has the greatest influence on predicting work satisfaction variance, these results prove (Owusu 2012) which states that “job satisfaction can be measured using indicators like employee motivation psychological well-being and working conditions”. for Therefore, to this extent this research proves that. Followed by Organizational Culture which is ($\beta= .41$), this results also proves what (Kilber et al.2014) said that the

“millennial generation have grown up multitasking between school, work and social activities”. Hence organizational culture is a strong indicator for job satisfaction.

Contrariwise, irrespective of the positive relationship these variables had with the dependent variable in the correlation analysis, the regression analysis, which is a model reveals that the work-life balance and leadership styles as independent variables with the values ($\beta = .005$) and ($\beta = -.039$) respectively even though had relationship with the dependent variable in the correlation analysis, did not have any impact or contributed to the dependent variable. There is a relationship anyway in the correlation analysis, but the regression shows that their individual relationship with the dependent is not significant. The hypothesized effects are presented in the regression analysis. Work-life balance, working conditions, leadership, and organizational culture all positively connected to job satisfaction, as predicted, with P- values for independent variables below the alpha value of 0.01.

Conclusion

This research has consciously achieved its research aims, as evidenced by the discussion of the findings in connection to the study's aims. Also, it has added a valuable contribution to the body of knowledge in regard to job satisfaction in the health sector, not leaving out practical information for health care leaders and policy makers. In addition, research shows that millennials have the highest undermining rates when it comes to health workers as any generation before them. (Robert Wood Johnson Foundation 2014). However, factors related to job satisfaction for health workers are misinterpreted (Bugajski et al., 2017), which intense contributes to their joy towards their jobs faster therefore the reason for the correlation and regression study is to examine which of these factors are highly contributed to employee job satisfaction for millennials. The theoretical foundation and framework for this study was Herzberg's two factor theory. The quantitative study was done by running a multiple linear regression and Pearson correlation analysis which were used to analyze an understand the link between the independent variable and the dependent variables the result indicated that all the independent variables were positively correlated with the dependent variable which is job satisfaction. It was discovered that respondents' thoughts or opinions suggested that KATH's activities included wellness activities, community mobilization activities, and educational programs, all of which are highly important activities that enable KATH personnel attract service value. The research also revealed that certain other criteria, such as gender, had little effect on health workers' behaviors, but that activities carried out by KATH in response to their patients have a significant impact on their workers' behaviors when it comes to job satisfaction.

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